

Mercer Wetland Project, Mercer County (40.49830, -84.56846)

Since construction in 2022, the main nutrient benefit of the Mercer Wetland Project has been filtration of inflows pumped from Grand Lake St. Marys. Nutrient concentrations throughout the Project suggest nutrient retention occurring within both Phase 1 and 2 overall. However, particulate matter enters Phase 2 (western portion) seasonally from the forested wetland pool, rendering that portion of the Project a source of total phosphorus on an annual scale. Due to the active management style of the Project and its inflow pump, drought conditions in 2024 would not have had a large role in nutrient filtration associated with the Project.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology of this Project is actively managed by ODNR staff. The Project has 29.7 acres of restored wetland, featuring two treatment trains (one per each phase) with a pump and multiple water level control structures (WLCS). In Phase 1, water is pumped in from Grand Lake St. Marys through a series of tiles under a corn field and into one of two shallow wetland pools, directed by WLCS. In Phase 2, water is pumped in from Grand Lake St. Marys into a pool. In both phases, water level in all pools and flow between pools is controlled using WLCS. Both phases are managed in a “raise and rest” type of style, in which the wetland pools are pumped full in early spring each year and refilled when water levels begin to drop, resulting in wetland pools that are permanently flooded year-round through the combined inputs from pumping and surface runoff events associated with heavy rains. The pump does not run during the winter. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as any time the pump is turned on or the Project receives 0.5” or more of rain.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar treatment train wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- To increase nutrient retention across the Project, the inflow pump for both phases should run more often to increase the hydraulic loading rate (volume of wetland inflow per wetland acres, HLR). An increase in HLR is often correlated with higher nutrient reduction rates, depending on the functionality of other aspects of the wetland (e.g., soil sorption, vegetation uptake).
- Another way to increase nutrient retention across both phases would be to seed/reseed Pool 2 in Phase 1 (second pool from the north in Phase 1) and all pools in Phase 2. Despite the Project operating for 1.5 years, no wetland plants have started to grow in these locations. It is possible the water in Pool 2 of Phase 1 is too deep for wetland plants to establish. If that is the case, the inflow pump would have to be turned off for an appropriate amount of time for vegetation to grow. While this would reduce the HLR in the short-term while plants become established, it could increase the Project’s potential nutrient retention in the long-term.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.